

ISic4421

Epitaph for Athanippos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

plinth

Editor

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited site

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

unnumbered tomb on the eastern margin of the excavated area of the necropolis (close to tomb 23) in contrada Cardusa , where it remains in situ

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Necropoli di Abakainon

Physical Description

Intact stele of the local sandstone belonging to a tomb of the epitymbion type B; the associated tomb monument has not been excavated.

Dimensions

Height 121 cm

Width 29 cm

Depth 12 cm

Layout

A single line of Greek letters filling the width of the stele, approximately 20 cm from the top of the stele.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plainly cut and fairly regular squarish letters. Alpha has broken bar (and in the first instance, shows a slight apex at the top); theta is smaller than other letters and mid-line, with a single central dot; nu has equal length vertical strokes (the right slightly off vertical); pi is quadrate in form with nearly equal length vertical strokes and slightly overlapping horizontal; omicron is slightly smaller than other letters and mid-line.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 29 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Ἀθανίππου

Apparatus

text as per Sofia 2018

Translation (en)

(tomb) of Athanippos

Commentary

The epitaph consists of a single name in the genitive, as with the majority of the epitaphs attested from this necropolis. The name Ἀθάνιππος [<http://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/name/%E1%BC%88%CE%B8%CE%AC%CE%BD%CE%B9%CF%80%CF%80%CE%BF%CF%82>] is not a common one, with only one other known (probably) Sicilian instance (IG II/III (2nd edn) 10293: Ἑρμῶν | Ἀθανίππου | Σικελὸς | ἀπὸ Τυνδαρίδος, a funerary inscription from Athens of the imperial period.

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

Sofia, G. 2018. Nuove iscrizioni funerarie dalla necropoli di Abakainon. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 206: 103-112. At 108 no.11 and fig.12

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